

Between NATO and a Hard Place: Defence Spending Debate in Germany and Czechia

Abstract: Defence spending has become a primary issue in the context of NATO. This article compares the behaviour of Germany and Czechia, two very similar countries that differ in size. Building on the small states literature, it asks how the size factor translates into the domestic debates and decisions. Based on expert and political debates it shows that while the German debate is much more detailed and informed than the Czech debate, the result of both is very similar. Both countries behave as small states in the area of defence spending. The result supports the theoretical view that size is an inherently relative concept in international relations and offers several new paths for future research.

Keywords: defence spending; small states; Germany; Czechia; NATO

Introduction

After more than two decades of benefiting from the peace dividend, the defence budgets are rising again in most European countries. This is good news for the North Atlantic Alliance (NATO), which has long encouraged its member states to invest more into defence capabilities, as well as for the United States whose representatives have long claimed that the US is bearing a disproportional burden in transatlantic security. However, spending more on defence is often unpopular among European publics – partly because it means less money for other causes, partly because Europeans have felt as secure as never before in the post-Cold War world (European Council 2003). The international pressure and domestic opposition cause a headache to the government representatives who struggle to sustain domestic legitimacy and to fulfil their international commitments.

International cooperation and integration have been identified as one of several factors that limit nation states' freedom of action and tie hands to the national governments (cf. Cooper 2004). Particularly in the European Union, the impact of institutions on state behaviour and options has been studied extensively (Cowles *et al.* 2001, Olsen 2002, Graziano and Vink 2007, Bulmer and Lequesne 2013). While much of the scholarship focused on policy areas where the supranational institutions had coercive power over the member states, there is a general agreement that national foreign and security policies have been subject to adaptation and limitation too (Torreblanca 2001, Irondelle 2003, Smith 2004b, Larsen 2005, Wong 2006, Miskimmon 2007, Gross 2011, Moumoutzis 2011, Palosaari 2011, Raimundo 2013), even if there is no common understanding of the mechanism of this influence (for a review see Tonra 2013). Foreign policy documents, declarations, and strategies adopted at the international level, such as the EU Global Strategy (EEAS 2016) and Council

conclusions, define a common understanding of the world as well as default reactions that steer the member states national debate and strategic documents. Similarly, NATO strategic concepts (NATO 1991, 1999, 2010) and summit declarations provide the same function for the allies. Both the EU's and NATO's influence over the member states' policies is further boosted by the massive institutional underpinning that develops the organisations' policy between major strategic debates, be it the European External Action Service and the Commission in case of the EU or the International Staff and International Military Staff in case of NATO. In the case of defence spending, however, we witness a clearly defined policy of the international organisation that transfers with huge difficulties to the national level.

Scholarly literature has addressed defence spending in Europe extensively but the accounts have been largely restricted to the analysis of the relationship between defence spending and economic indicators (Paul 1996, Kollias 2008), on the development of capabilities (Sperling 2004, James 2006, Bove and Cavatorta 2012), and its link to the development of the EU's common security and defence policy (Mawdsley 2004, cf. Posen 2006). Besides, there is abundance of think tank outputs that focus on the policy side of the defence spending conundrum (Schmitt 2003, Liberti 2011, Ortega 2017, Brustlein 2018). There are significantly fewer accounts connecting the institutional setup of the European security policy to domestic politics. Most such works focus on the national preference between NATO and the EU and their impact on the institution building, particularly on the CSDP (Hofmann 2011, Menon 2011, Pannier and Schmitt 2014, Heisbourg 2016). This article aims at enhancing this debate by linking the issue of defence spending and its domestic acceptance to the small state literature. It asks to what extent size plays a role in the domestic deliberations about defence spending and the political strategies to increase national investment in defence.

Within a common institutional framework, states have a different room for manoeuvre. Despite nominally equal, literature has long recognised that larger states command more influence over events than smaller countries. In anarchic international relations, small states were considered "marginal at best and counterproductive at worst" (Smed and Wivel 2017, p. 81). They cannot expect to have much influence on the shape of things, and they need to adopt specific strategies to ensure their survival (Walt 1987, Snyder 1997, cf. Kassab 2018). In a more orderly environment provided by a hegemon or institutional order, such as the one in Europe, however, small states can thrive (Wivel *et al.* 2014). They can focus on more than mere survival and, indeed, help shape international politics (Bunse 2009, Panke 2012, Vandecasteele *et al.* 2013, Bossuyt 2017, Haugevik 2017, Smed and Wivel 2017, Weiss 2017, Corbett *et al.* 2018).

At the same time, however, small states remain "structurally disadvantaged" (Panke 2010). The bigger and richer countries have more power to persuade their partners with threats, side-offers, or issue-linkages (Pedersen 1998, cf. Hayes-Renshaw and Wallace 2006, p. 252, Hix and Høyland 2011, Thomson 2011, p. 212ff). Bigger countries are generally believed to have more viable alternatives to a negotiated solution, the so-called "outside option" (cf. Moravcsik 1993, p. 500, Voeten 2001), which makes them less willing to make concessions and more likely to have greater influence over the result. Counterintuitively, this is also true for intergovernmental negotiations, in which all states are nominally equal. In the European Union, for example, where policy-making in some areas (particularly foreign and security policy) is still subject to unanimous decisions and thus lends every single state, disregarding the

size, the power of veto, scholars have long argued that the practice does not necessarily follow the theory (Smith 2004a, Stetter 2004, cf. Sjursen 2011). Unlike bigger countries, smaller member states need to use their veto parsimoniously and link it directly with the key national interest in the debate in order not to lose too much political capital in the recurring negotiations (Tallberg 2008, p. 691). Small states can use other ways to promote their interest to make up for the deficit in size, such as arguing (Risse 2000) and nominating experienced negotiators (Meerts 1997), and become surprisingly successful in international negotiations (Golub 2012). But it is hard. International institutions benefit small states, but do not “overcome or work outside of international political realities” (Hey 2003, p. 188) so the general expectation needs to be that bigger members are more likely to shape the negotiation results according to their preferences.

Defence spending has become one of the key security issues of the current debates in both NATO and the EU. At the Wales summit in 2014, NATO members pledged to reverse the decline in defence spending and to “aim to move towards” defence budgets at the level of 2 per cent of their GDP. Out of this budget, they should spend 20 per cent on investments, and research and development (NATO 2014). The EU has not adopted any such concrete measure but has launched several initiatives that nudge member states to invest more in defence, including the European Defence Fund (EDF) and Permanent Structured Cooperation in defence (PESCO). While the NATO pledge had to be adopted unanimously, the EU initiatives, particularly PESCO, did not require support from all member states. Nevertheless, with the exception of the UK, which had already decided to leave the EU, Denmark, which had an opt-out from CSDP, and Malta restricted by constitutional limitations, all EU members decided to take part.

This article asks how the NATO’s decision on defence spending was reflected in the domestic debates and policies in Germany and Czechia, two countries that share many characteristics but differ in one specific aspect – their size.¹ Both countries belong to laggards among NATO countries which in 2014 were spending only 1.18 and 0.95 per cent of GDP respectively on defence, out of which they spent respectively 12.94 and 6.53 per cent on equipment (NATO 2018a). The public opinion in both countries never considered defence expenditure an important topic. In Czechia, more than 50 per cent of respondents viewed defence spending as a vain strain on the state budget steadily between 2001 and 2013 (CVVM 2018). Similarly, the GMF Transatlantic Trends showed the German population’s preference for maintaining or even decreasing the current levels of spending in 2011-2013 (GMF 2011, 2012, 2013). The expectation based on the literature briefly overviewed above is that bigger states are more capable of influencing the decision-making at the international level and have more outside options. The German government, thus, should be expected to be happy with the decision it subscribed to, or ignore it and follow the domestic preference. Czechia, by contrast, has a limited power to shape the international decision, but restricted outside options. As a result, its government would try either to shape the domestic debate to accept the international commitments or to pretend to be both fulfilling the commitments and complying with the domestic expectations.

Germany and Czechia do not share just a location in Central Europe, shielded from potential enemies by neighbouring allies and partners. They have taken a rather similar path over the past 30 years in defence policy. They passed two major internal

reforms. First, the Bundeswehr had to ingest the former DDR-forces after the German unification and the Czech Army had to establish itself after the split of Czechoslovakia. A decade later, both militaries transformed from an army based on conscription into a professional all-volunteer force. In the meantime, they had completely revisited their tasks and doctrines and became expeditionary forces deployable in overseas theatres under NATO and EU flags. Over this time, the armed forces of both countries shrunk significantly and lost sizable parts of their budgets. Even when the trend reversed in the mid-2010s and Europeans started investing more into defence, Germany and Czechia remained the only countries in their region whose investment share kept sinking (Béraud-Sudreau and Giegerich 2018).

The domestic debate in both Germany and Czechia is understood as containing three parts here. Firstly, there is the expert debate on defence policy that cultivates the concepts and relations for policymakers and the public to make their decision. Secondly, political parties translate their understanding of security threats and responses into election manifestos, governmental policy statements and coalition agreements. Lastly, the budget discussions in the parliament represent the views of the audience that needs to be persuaded to invest more into defence. The analysis is based on qualitative interpretative approach, tracing how individuals refer to the 2 per cent guideline and the issue of the Transatlantic burden sharing in the debate as well as what other arguments they use to support or oppose the budget increase. Public opinion polls are not used as a source because they lack regularity and comparability, both within the countries and between them. The parliaments' budgetary deliberations seem to be a more appropriate place to read what forms the internal debate on defence spending in the respective countries, even if the parliamentarians are mere representatives and their views surely differ from the population as a whole.

Both Germany and Czechia held general elections in autumn 2013 and 2017. The two campaigns offer the opportunity to compare how the thinking of political parties shifted over time, and how the Wales pledge and Donald Trump's ascent influence the parties' programmes. Similarly, the governments' policy statements and coalition agreements reflect how the party promises are translated into a concrete political programme. Further, the first two budgetary debates of all governments are studied (2014 and 2015, and 2018 and 2019) to trace the arguments used in relation to defence spending and the way in which the parliamentarians refer to NATO commitments.

In what follows, the article first introduces the context of the 2 per cent guideline and how it features in the transatlantic security debate. It identifies two key moments of politicisation – the Wales summit and the ascension of Donald Trump. Next, the German and Czech debates are analysed. The final part compares the findings with the theoretical expectations and concludes.

The 2 per cent guideline and its adoption in NATO

The debate over burden sharing is as old as the NATO itself (James 2006). The US has always complained that it invests disproportionately more into European security than Europeans do. While there is no agreement in the literature whether European were free-riding during the Cold War and post-Cold War period (cf. Gadea *et al.* 2004, George and Sandler 2018, Jakobsen 2018), it is clear that this has been the perception in

the US for a long time. However, the decrease of defence budgets after 1990 occurred on both sides of the Atlantic. If there were any criticism involved, it targeted the inefficiency of the military reform that did not allow the budget to sink faster (Aufrant 1999). Only after 2001 when the American budget started rising due to the ongoing war on terror, while the European budgets remained stagnant or even further declined, the gap became obvious and a topic of heated political debate (Sandler and Shimizu 2014).

The 2 per cent guideline first appeared in 2002 when NATO requested that candidate countries committed “sufficient resources” while bidding for a membership. Given the current state of defence spending in the candidate countries, the number seemed realistic and motivational at the same time (Lunn and Williams 2017, p. 6, Krause 2019). After all, all allies had been spending 2 per cent of their GDP on defence without major troubles in 1990. The 2 per cent commitment did not bind the member states, even though the US argued that the allies should stick to it for the sake of credibility towards the candidates. As a result, many European allies’ defence budgets kept falling (as a percentage of the GDP), as did those of most new members immediately after accession (NATO 2011).

The trouble with the European defence budgets is not just their size. The problem is the obvious inability of the European militaries to fulfil the tasks that the politicians and publics expect from them (Sperling 2004, cf. Coonen 2006, Hallams and Schreer 2012). The transformation to an expeditionary and all-volunteer force that occurred in many European countries during the first two decades after the end of the Cold War was very costly (cf. Bove and Cavatorta 2012) and has taken its toll on European capabilities. Over the years, American representatives intensified their push for a fairer burden sharing, meaning primarily more European spending (Gates 2011). The result was the Wales pledge in 2004.

The Wales summit took place in a specific strategic situation. After decades of out-of-area operations, NATO decided to re-emphasise territorial defence following the Russian annexation of Crimea. This involved designing the Very High Readiness Joint Task Force and, later, the establishment of the enhanced forward presence in the Baltic countries and in Poland (Ringsmose and Rynning 2017, Zapfe 2017). Addressing the dismal state of European defence spending, the allies pledged to halt any further decrease, to aim to increase it in real terms, and to aim to move towards the 2 per cent and the 20 per cent investment share respectively within a decade, i.e. by 2024 (NATO 2014). While it needs to be emphasised that the member states only committed to aiming to reach the guideline, it was still the first time that the numbers appeared in the summit declaration, endorsed by the heads of states and governments. As it is usually the case with such international declarations once agreed, the subsequent summits have repeated and confirmed it (NATO 2016, 2018b).

The importance of the defence spending issue has grown with Donald Trump’s presidency. The candidate Trump turned the burden-sharing in NATO into a major campaign issue (Besch 2016) and followed on as a president. He has been the first US president to question the US commitment to European security, connecting the US guarantees to the level of individual countries’ budget on defence. Even though no change occurred in the official texts issued by NATO (NATO 2018b), Trump’s rhetoric managed to narrow down the issue of transatlantic security cooperation to a single issue – defence spending (cf. Birnbaum 2018). In a characteristically chaotic manner, the US president first criticised allies for freeriding, warned that 2 per cent level of spending

needed to be achieved as soon as possible, increased the requested level of spending to 4 per cent, and later signed the summit declaration, which maintained the 2 per cent guideline unchanged, boasting of his ability to change allies' positions.

The 2 per cent pledge has played an important role in simplifying the issue of defence spending and the need for the Europeans to play a greater role in ensuring their own security. As an indicator, however, it is fundamentally flawed. Most scholars agree that Europeans need to spend more on defence,² but they criticise the focus on input that the current pledge embodies. Instead of measuring security by how much money is spent, they argue that it needs to be evaluated by how much it responds to current and future threats and creates necessary military capabilities (Mölling 2014, Biscop 2017, Krause 2019). In particular, by linking the defence spending to the GDP, it connects two factors that are not mutually dependent. A growing economy does not result in increased threats vice versa. Paradoxically, a country may meet the criteria and become less capable when the GDP falls quicker than defence spending, due to long-term contractual obligations of the state budget (Major 2015).

German and Czech debate on defence spending

This part presents the three types of debates that have occurred in Germany and Czechia on the topic of the defence spending and NATO commitments. First, the expert debate is reviewed to show the knowledge base upon which the political debates take place. Second, the two sets of election manifestos are reviewed to find out whether any conceptual shift occurred between 2013 and 2017. Lastly, the budgetary debates are summed up to show how the issue of defence spending translated into specific decisions at the national level.

Expert debate

There is one parliament in Germany and one in Czechia. There is always one national budget in each of the countries. The difference in size matters, however, when we look at the expert debate, because there are many more institutes and many more researchers dealing with security in Germany than there are in Czechia. The debate is, therefore, deeper and more inclusive, touching upon all issues in Germany. In Czechia, by contrast, the pool is rather limited and some issues simply do not find their researcher to make an informed point about them (cf. Weiss 2018, pp. 170–171).

German experts have published extensively on the issue of defence spending. The sore state of Bundeswehr after years of austerity has deserved a lot of coverage, particularly from the perspective of future objectives and developments (Dickow and Linnenkamp 2016, Schütz 2016) and when new solutions were proposed (Major and Mölling 2014, Allers 2016). Due to the fact that Bundeswehr is a “parliamentary army”, unlike in other countries, the shortcomings of both the military and the structures surrounding it have been addressed transparently every year in the reports of the parliamentary commissioner (for one of the recent reports see Parliamentary Commissioner for the Armed Forces 2018). The 2 per cent guideline of NATO quickly became a topic for policy papers and analyses. While acknowledging that Germany needs to invest more on defence and take on more responsibility within the Alliance and in security policy more general, most German experts denounced the 2 per cent

guideline for being arbitrary and illogical. Several arguments appear in the German expert debate. Firstly, the false connection between the defence spending and GDP is targeted with the notion that threats and shortcomings should drive defence budgets, not the state of economy. Secondly, the input-oriented design of the indicator rates poorly in the reviews because the mere fact of spending a lot of money does not mean spending efficiently (a long-term weakness of the federal defence ministry) nor acquiring capabilities needed for effective deployment and international cooperation. Lastly, German experts criticise the absolute amounts that Germany should be spending according to the NATO guideline. They question the ability of Bundeswehr and the federal ministry to manage that many major projects to require such monies, as well as the political desirability of Germany becoming the largest defence spender in Europe by far. Instead of the 2 per cent, Germany should focus on making the procurement system more efficient and sustaining the ongoing projects of internationalisation and cooperation that, in the longer term, make Europeans more capable and interoperable.

In comparison to the German expert debate, the Czech discussions are much more limited and shallower. There are contributions focusing on the military finances, their sustainability and reasons for the existing structural debt (Pernica 2011, Kufčák 2015). The ministry of defence has also conducted a similar analysis, acknowledging that the costs of transformation in combination with falling budgets have produced an unsustainable situation (Ministry of Defence of the Czech Republic 2011). Most of the expert outputs in the Czech debate, however, focus on explaining the internal workings of the two security organisations of which Czechia is a member and new initiatives launched at the international level, such as the EU battle groups and PESCO (Krásný and Socha 2007, Kolín 2018). When the Wales 2 per cent pledge appears in the expert debate, it remains largely undisputed. Even where the authors argue that the measure is “fetishized” at the level of NATO, they do not draw conclusions to an alternative Czech policy and even argue that there still is a need to commit resources (Kufčák 2016).

Election manifestos and governmental statements

General elections in 2013 and 2017 in Germany led to the same result: a victory of Christian Democratic Union and a “grand coalition” between the CDU/CSU and social democrats (SPD). The two parties entered both campaigns as the main contestants, however, which made them seek differences from each other. In 2017 it was particularly difficult because the campaign took place after four years of joint government by the two (technically three) parties.

In 2013, most of political parties proposed cutting the defence budget as well as the military more generally.³ In an extreme version, Die Linke campaigned for a withdrawal from all overseas missions and operations (including CSDP police missions), reduction and disarmament of Bundeswehr, and re-investing the money saved into civilian peace corps (Die Linke 2013, pp. 52–53). The Greens did not go as far as that but still suggested cutting the defence budget that they considered guided by the defence industry demands too much (B90/Die Grünen 2013, p. 309). They suggested a reduction of military forces that would be possible thanks to more integration at the European level, which was a point strongly advocated by social democrats as well (SPD 2013, pp. 111–112). The more to the right of the political spectrum, the more parties avoided mentioning budget cuts. Manifesto of free

democrats argued for ensuring the deployability of Bundeswehr through “appropriate funding” (FDP 2013, p. 91), even if they did not specify what exactly they deemed appropriate. Similarly, the CDU/CSU mentioned the need for “sustainability of financing” and wanted to ensure “planning security and reliability” (CDU/CSU 2013, p. 76) but they failed to note what exactly that would mean. At the same time, the manifesto clearly prioritised financial stability in Germany and in Europe as an overarching topic. The coalition agreement between CDU, CSU, and SPD did not address the question of defence budget at all (CDU *et al.* 2013).

Four years later, the picture could not look more different. The 2 per cent pledge was referred to in all parties’ manifestos, even if only implicitly sometimes. It became a crucial topic of division between the left and the right. CDU/CSU, which had run the defence ministry since 2005, praised itself for a turnaround in defence financing and a first growth in defence budget after 25 years. The party clearly stated that it aimed at increasing the defence budget gradually to 2 per cent of GDP “as agreed at the NATO summit in 2014 in Wales”. As if expecting opposition, the manifesto emphasised that the money is aimed at defence against external threats, that the guideline was adopted “unanimously by the Alliance and with the then US president Obama”. It also listed the support of the whole coalition of the time, which included SPD, and framed the pledge as “an issue of reliability too” (CDU/CSU 2017, p. 65). To prevent accusations of excessive militarisation, the CDU/CSU connected the raise in defence spending with a raise in official development assistance (ODA) in the same amount up to the level of 0.7 per cent of GDP. The social democrats, by contrast, acknowledged the need to build capable forces, well paid and well equipped, which requires a “necessary increase in the defence budget” (SPD 2017, p. 105). They strongly opposed, however, a “fully unnecessary and unrealistic increase rate of the German defence budget” (SPD 2017, p. 106), quoting specifically the 2 per cent indicator. The manifesto argued that such a raise would mean doubling the current amount, which was not realistic, and criticised the indicator more generally, because security and stability could not be measured by defence spending. The coalition agreement did not mention any spending levels but claims that means must be “significantly boosted to manage the immense international challenges”. This should be done both in the defence and development areas where the budget should be increased in 1:1 ratio (CDU *et al.* 2018, pp. 144–145).

The smaller parties differed widely in their approach. The extreme right AfD was, maybe paradoxically when compared to other right-wing parties in Europe, the most open to the 2 per cent objective, arguing for a more just burden sharing. The increased defence spending should achieve more German and European influence in NATO, help turning NATO into a “pure defence alliance” again, and make German forces deployable (AfD 2017, pp. 18–19). The extreme left, on the other hand, called for “significant decrease” of the defence budget (Die Linke 2017, p. 12), disarmament of Bundeswehr, its transformation from a deployment force, and a German exit from the NATO military structures (Die Linke 2017, pp. 100–101). The two centrist parties took a middle ground, while still very critical to the government’s approach. The FDP agreed with a budget increase in order to make Bundeswehr capable of both territorial defence and overseas deployment, but lambasted inefficient procurement processes. The manifesto did not openly declared the party’s position to the NATO’s 2 per cent indicator, but argued for a joint spending for defence and development at the level of 3 per cent of GDP (FDP 2017, pp. 100–101). The Greens shared the criticism of defence

procurement system but argued that Bundeswehr needed clearer political priorities and European cooperation instead of more money. They rejected the 2 per cent objective and advocated more money in development assistance (B90/Die Grünen 2017, p. 87).

In Czechia, there are generally more parties in the parliament, which means more election manifestos, but not necessarily more arguments on defence spending. In 2013, some parties did not address defence at all (extreme right-wing party Úsvit) or did not address the defence budget (communist KSČM). Most major parties both on the right and left emphasized the need for Czechia to be an “active and responsible member of [...] the North Atlantic Alliance” (ČSSD 2013, p. 32, compare ODS 2013, p. 26, ANO 2011 2013), but did not make direct connection between responsibility and investment. Unlike in Germany, several parties argued for a “stabilisation” (TOP 09 2013, p. 24) or even an increase in defence spending (ODS 2013, p. 26) in 2013. The Christian democratic KDU-ČSL advocated an increase to the level of 1.5 per cent of GDP while mentioning that a NATO commitment was 2 per cent in the same sentence and conditioning the increase by a growth of GDP (sic!) (KDU-ČSL 2013, p. 12). The government’s policy statement did not address the level of defence spending at all. It only stated that “defence capabilities need to be developed” and the government shall “seek adjustments in the financing of the Ministry so as to ensure the necessary development of the armed forces” (Government of the Czech Republic 2014, sec. 3.15)

In 2017, the debate shifted, and the size of the defence budget became the key issue. While most manifestos did not elaborate on detailed arguments, many argued for an increase on the basis of “responsibility” (KDU-ČSL 2017, p. 12), “living up to promises” (TOP 09 2017, p. 14), “commitments” (ODS 2017, p. 11, STAN 2017, p. 50), and being “reliable partner” (ANO 2011 2017, p. 21). Most parties acknowledged the commitment to reach 2 per cent of GDP level by 2024 or earlier, with the exception of social democrats aiming at 1.4 per cent (ČSSD 2017, p. 29) and extreme right SPD’s 1.6 per cent (SPD 2016, p. 21). None of the latter numbers deserved any reasoning in the respective manifestos. Generally, there were very few conceptual ideas on defence spending in the parties’ proclamations. Only the Pirates and conservative TOP09 briefly mentioned an establishment of a multi-year fund to finance strategic procurement projects to replace the yearly budgetary planning of the defence ministry (Piráti 2017, p. 10, TOP 09 2017, p. 20). The policy statement of the minority ANO and ČSSD government pledged to “gradually increase the defence budget” to 1.4 per cent of GDP by 2021. It did not mention any connection of the defence spending to NATO debate but claimed to play “an active role in the UN, the EU, NATO and other organisations” (Government of the Czech Republic 2018, p. 19).

Parliamentary debates⁴

There are significant procedural differences between the processes of the parliamentary budget approval in Germany and in Czechia. First and foremost, the German parliament reserves much more time for a detailed discussion on individual chapters of the budget. Secondly, the budget for the year following the general elections is drafted by the new government in Germany, which means that its adoption only occurs during the year for which the budget is proposed. In Czechia, by contrast, the incoming governments accepted the draft budgets prepared by their predecessors and rushed it through the parliament within a couple of weeks in December. The latter difference does not,

however, necessarily limit the possibility of the Czech parliamentarians to put forward arguments and proposals for budget alteration.

The German parliamentary debates over the 2014 budget took place after the Russian annexation of Crimea but before the Wales NATO summit. The overall topic of the debate was budget consolidation, meaning mainly budget cuts. There was no expectation of more money for defence, “at least not in the upcoming years” (SPD, 9 April 2014). The 2 per cent level was mentioned in the debate but brushed aside by the defence minister as a wrong issue for the debate, even though she recognized the need to react to allies’ requests based on the Crimean crisis (25 June 2014). Her party representatives argued that 2 per cent spending would be nice but a sustainable budget consolidation was needed (CDU/CSU, 25 June 2014).

The mood changed only slightly after Wales when Bundestag debated the 2015 budget. CDU/CSU recognized the 2 per cent as a long-term objective “without question” (CDU/CSU, 9 September 2014) and even SPD admitted that it should be reached within the next ten years (SPD, 26 November 2014). There was no doubt, however, that it did not have much relevance for the current budget. Even the defence minister did not advocate budget increase, but just refused further cuts (10 September 2014). In shorter term, she just pledged for increasing the spending efficiency, the lack of which was broadly criticised by many Bundestag members (SPD, Greens, 10 September; Linke, 26 November 2014). SPD believed 2 per cent were “not doable” for Germany because the ministry was unable to spend so much money and politically, it would be problematic in relations with the UK and France (SPD, 10 September 2014).

The debates in 2018 (budgets for 2018 and 2019) touched upon the 2 per cent pledge most of the time. Generally, most parties agreed that an increase was necessary, with the exception of Die Linke that criticised the government for “hasty” acceptance of Donald Trump’s demands (Linke, 12 September 2018) and the Greens who wanted to improve spending rather than to increase it (Greens, 8 November 2018). They differed, however, in their target level of spending and the role of NATO pledge in setting the right level. For AfD, there was a commitment, which should be met (AfD, 16 May 2018). For CDU/CSU, it was a target and Germany had to take its responsibility seriously (CDU/CSU, 21 November 2018) as it “owed it to its allies and soldiers” (CDU/CSU, 12 September 2018), but was happy with modest increases towards 1.5 per cent by 2024 what their minister labelled “an ambitious objective” (21 November 2018). Other parties rejected the 2 per cent as a false measure (SPD, 16 May 2018) that blurred the important debate on military reform (FDP, 21 November 2018), and the budget increase was necessary with respect to concrete procurement projects, not to “some NATO quota” (SPD, 21 November 2018).

Czech parliamentary debates were on one hand much shorter than the German ones. On the other hand, NATO commitments were present in the discussion irrespective of the year, even if not in the form of the 2 per cent pledge. The 2014 budget discussed in December 2013, before both Crimea and Wales, was not particularly controversial in respect to defence. It was one of the last austerity budgets with cuts across all areas. The minister of defence pleaded to the parliament to reject further budget cuts introduced by the budget committee that would “disrupt [Czech] credibility in relations to the Alliance and allies” (16 December 2013) but did not succeed. The following year, the 2 per cent pledge was explicitly mentioned. The opposition representative reminded that Czechia “had promised 2 per cent of GDP to

the allies before entering NATO” and argued that this ratio was, among others, a measure of the country’s “willingness to invest into defence and to be a fully-fledged ally” (ODS, 3 December 2014). She also expressed her regret that an agreement among political leaders to increase defence budget to 2 per cent of GDP by 2025 had failed in 2014 and the government only declared its commitment to reach 1.4 per cent during that period (Smlouva koaličních stran o zajištění obrany České republiky 2014).

The size of the defence budget was slightly more prominent in the 2018 and 2019 budget debates. While the government’s representatives did not deem necessary to explain the exact size of the (slowly rising) defence budget, opposition once again criticised the slow increase and tabled a proposal to reallocate additional funds. The 2 per cent indicator is mentioned both as a NATO’s “recommendation” and as a “commitment” (ODS, 15 December 2017). The existence of a structural debt in military equipment and the deteriorating security environment were both mentioned as the reason why Czechia should “send a clear signal that [it is] an ally to be taken into account”. Similar proposals were tabled by opposition parliamentarians one year later to increase the defence budget, which was “roughly a half of what NATO demands” (TOP09, 5 December 2018). The parliament rejected all those proposals. Others were more sceptical, however. The Pirates argued for a more limited increase of the defence budget fearing the inability of the ministry to spend the money efficiently (Piráti, 5 December 2018). From the left, the rise of the defence budget was criticised by some because, while not disputing Czech obligations and needs, “even richer countries do not meet the 2 per cent for military” (ČSSD, 5 December 2018).

Interestingly enough, both in Germany and in Czechia, the opposition tried to incorporate their view of the 2 per cent pledge into law. In Germany, Die Linke tabled a proposal to reject the 2 per cent pledge and bind the government to withdraw the German agreement officially in NATO. While many parliamentarians expressed their reservations to the target and its significance (19 January 2018), the proposal was clearly rejected by Bundestag with backing restricted to Die Linke and the Greens only. In Czechia, by contrast, the conservative opposition tabled a proposal that would, if adopted, oblige the government to draft budgets committing 2 per cent of last year’s GDP on defence (Černochová 2017). The authors argued that the law would merely codify an existing Czech commitment, it would help improve Czech image in NATO, and help stabilise long-term financial planning in the defence sector. The proposal was rejected by the parliament in the first reading.

Conclusions

Defence spending has become an important issue in international and domestic debates on European security. In Wales in 2014, NATO member states officially pledged to spend 2 per cent of their GDP on defence by 2024. The domestic debate often differs, however, from what is discussed and concluded internationally. This article has analysed the defence spending debate in two European countries, Germany and Czechia, that share many common features and differ significantly in their size. The objective has been to study how size has influenced the approach to defence spending in these countries with the focus on three types of debate – expert, election/governmental, and parliamentary.

The impact of the size difference can mostly be seen on the richness and depth of the domestic debate on defence spending. In Germany, the broad expert background provides a plethora of arguments about defence budgets and the feasibility of the NATO's 2 per cent measure. These arguments spill over to the political debate and are used by parties and politicians in both the election manifestos (in a more concise version) and parliamentary debates. In Czechia, the argumentation is either missing altogether or it is limited to very short statements that lack the in-depth understanding of the practical dynamics behind defence budgets' construction.

Political arguments are important in both countries as the size of any part of the budget is a primary political issue. In Czechia, the political argumentation for increasing defence spending is based on NATO's commitments and expectations above all. While the structural necessity to improve the national military force and to provide soldiers with decent pay and appropriate equipment appears in the debate too, the international pressure seems to be a much more important factor in the debate. In Germany, the internal need to adapt to the changing security environment and to remedy structural deficiencies of the Bundeswehr features more strongly in the debate. The allies' pressure is, however, an important factor too. This can be illustrated on the interventions of some conservative members of the parliament who accept that Germany must adjust to NATO's expectations after Wales. There is, at the same time, a much stronger and pronounced opposition to the 2 per cent measure that, even if not disputing the importance of NATO, questions the relevance of the indicator.

The result of the debate has been very similar in both countries. Disregarding how sophisticated or broad the debate about defence spending is, the budgets are rising in both countries, albeit very slowly. Neither of the two countries seems to be on the track to reach the 2 per cent level by 2024 and they do not even seem to be trying very hard, in fact. The German government is, however, slightly more open about its lack of commitment than Czech politicians are.

To come back to the expectations from the small and big states formulated in the introduction to this article, both Germany and Czechia tend to behave as small countries when it comes to defence spending. While not disputing the commitment internationally and adjusting policies slightly in line with it, they use the argument of international pressure to sway the domestic debate and at the same time, do not push the point too hard so that the domestic political costs are minimal. In short, they muddle through – acknowledge the international obligations and comply with domestic expectations. This finding clearly shows that size needs to be understood in relative terms in international relations. Even the biggest European country, Germany, behaves as a small state in certain areas and relations. It also bids for further research. Two paths seem to be most relevant. Firstly, a cross-policy comparison of German behaviour could offer an insight into the reasons behind the “small” behaviour in defence area. Secondly, a broader comparison including more European countries could identify additional factors, such as history, geographical location, that shape the behaviour of both big and small countries in European security.

Notes

1. The concept of size remains contested despite being widely used in the academic debate (Archer and Nugent 2002, Rickli 2008). Some base the definition on objective criteria,

particularly geographic or demographic size of the country or the gross domestic product (Vital 1967). Others prefer the position of states in the system and focus on their influence (Maass 2016). And others focus on a state's position relative to others (Thorhallsson and Wivel 2006) or self-perception (Crandall and Varov 2016). By all accounts, Germany remains a big state whereas Czechia is a small one in the context of European security.

2. Very few argue that the current level of funding should remain unchanged (Biscop 2017) or even is too high (Robinson 2017).
3. Alternative für Deutschland (AfD) did stand in the 2013 general elections but removed its manifesto from the website. It is not available on other websites either and could not be included in the analysis.
4. The minutes of the respective lower chambers' plenaries have been used as a source, accessible on the websites of the institutions. The arguments in the debate are cited by the date and party affiliation of the speaker. Although a more detailed discussion usually takes place in the respective committees, their minutes are not published and could not be subject to analysis.

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